

PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AND METHODS OF A LAW TEACHER

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Annotation: This article discusses the professionalism and teaching methods of teachers of law.

Keywords: skill, pattern, method, law, lesson, education, society, educator, task, teacher.

INTRODUCTION

The teaching profession is one of the oldest professions in the world. Its social significance and need does not diminish with the development of human society, as education and upbringing are constant phenomena. If the experience accumulated by people had not been passed down from generation to generation, human society would not have developed. So, the emergence of the teaching profession is an objective reality. The word educator is derived from the Greek word for:

- 1) a person engaged in practical work, upbringing, teaching and educating children and youth and having special training in this area;
- 2) a scientist who develops theoretical problems of pedagogy.

The teacher is the mediator between society and the younger generation. It is a trusted representative of society. Teacher - transmits the knowledge, cultural and historical experience accumulated by mankind from generation to generation; it develops the experience. Teaching and learning are the two main tasks of teaching. These functions are always preserved, only the content changes: the demands of life and society on the individual change; the goals and objectives of education and upbringing are changing; a new content of education, upbringing, teaching is born; new methods and forms of teacher work. The master of his work is a highly cultured specialist with a deep knowledge of his subject, a good knowledge of the relevant fields of science or art, a practical knowledge of psychology, and methods of teaching and upbringing.

MAIN PART

The essence of pedagogical skills is a set of personal characteristics that provide a high level of self-organization of professional activity. These characteristics include the teacher's humanistic orientation, his or her professional knowledge, pedagogical ability, and pedagogical techniques. Components of a teacher: general culture, knowledge; high level of professional ethics; professional knowledge; pedagogical methods, technology; have pedagogical skills (communicative, perceptive, suggestive, constructive, cognitive, organizational, didactic, creative, research), as well as advanced pedagogical techniques (high communication culture, speech culture and technique, culture of appearance, emotions and relationships); their self-government; intuition, creative inspiration; learning and creative use of ideas and elements of someone's experience; selfeducation).

The structure of professional and pedagogical skills of a teacher is divided into constructive, organizational, communicative, gnostic activity. The above aspects are complemented by the following proposed functions: information, education and development, referral, mobilization, research. Who is a teacher today, especially a law teacher? He must enter the classroom with confidence, speak to the child and his family in a language that everyone understands, be competitive with the family and the child, and have sufficient knowledge of modern pedagogy, information technology, and so on.

The main features of pedagogical skills are the following qualities:

- 1) Citizenship (social responsibility; readiness of an individual to make an active, energetic contribution to solving social problems);
- 2) love for children (humanity, kindness, sensitivity, attentiveness, sincerity, kindness, etc.);
- 3) optimism (belief in the strength and potential of positive student development);
- 4) fairness (honesty, integrity, ability to be impartial);
- 5) politeness (pedagogical tact, politeness);
- 6) demanding of himself and children (responsibility, organization, self-criticism, conscientiousness, honesty, discipline, pride, self-esteem, rationality, modesty, initiative, activism);
- 7) altruism - devotion (concern for the welfare of others);
- 8) volitional qualities (purposefulness - "goal reflex", endurance, self-control, composure, perseverance, strength, patience, courage);
- 9) tolerance - tolerance towards people, forgiveness;
- 10) pedagogical observation (cognition, pedagogical vigilance);
- 11) empathy (the ability to understand the inner, mental (emotional) state of the student and to sympathize with this state not only in words but also in deeds; emotional sensitivity);
- 12) intelligence (charm, spirituality);
- 13) modernity (the teacher has a sense of belonging to the same period as his students);
- 14) dominance (efficiency, leadership tendency, acceptance responsibility for others, leadership skills);
- 15) creativity (creativity).

The above qualities are the superior qualities of the personality of a law teacher. In the absence of any of them, a law teacher can not effectively carry out pedagogical activities. There are also very important qualities of a law teacher: 1) the ability to dedicate oneself to one's favorite work - passion, suitability for pedagogical purposes; 2) people, a high level of responsibility to society for the results of their work. Research by educators has found that not everyone can be a teacher. Mastering it with all the mass character of the teaching profession requires: a more rigid structure of personal qualities and abilities, as well as a certain socio-psychological tendency to the work of the teacher. Pindus Journal Of Culture, Literature, and ELT

It should also be borne in mind that the quality of professional training of a law teacher does not depend on the amount of knowledge acquired (although this factor is very important in itself), but on the development of his emotional and motivational field. creative pedagogical thinking processes, pedagogical skills and pedagogical techniques.

Pedagogical excellence is the activity of a teacher with a high level of professionalism. Externally, it is manifested in the successful creative solution of various pedagogical tasks, the effective achievement of methods and goals of educational work. From the inside, it is the existing system of knowledge, abilities, skills, mental processes, personality traits that ensure the performance of pedagogical tasks. From the outside, it is a high and constantly evolving art of education and upbringing that is available to every teacher who works in the profession and

loves children. A master teacher is a sensitive and thoughtful teacher, a skilled educator who has thoroughly mastered modern methods of teaching and educational work.

Formation of mastering is carried out in the following stages: to get acquainted with the literature on this topic; Development of a plan to improve pedagogical skills: hypothesis, study, observation, and the best practices of colleagues etc.; The results of scientific research and the introduction of best practices directly into their own practice, self-education, etc. Consequently, vocational education - professional activity - is a broad self-education. There are currently five categories of legal teachers in modern education:

1. Educator-innovators. It is the definition of teachers that brings innovation to all elements of the pedagogical system. Their work is related to the introduction of local innovations, expressed in changing the content of social science courses.

2. Creative teachers (20%). These are teachers who bring innovation to their professional ways of working. Methodological techniques and changes in teaching methods dominate in the professional abilities of this category of teachers.

3. Most teachers are conscientious workers. Their role in the transition from the traditional model of school activities to the innovative model is not insignificant.

4. Teacher-formalists, who make up the majority of teachers, cannot work in an innovative mode.

5. Random people - 2%. Currently, a professional standard of pedagogical activity is proposed, a system of requirements that a teacher must meet in order to function has been developed. It defines the main powers of a teacher:

Competence to stimulate students' learning activities;

Competence to reveal the personal meaning of a particular educational course and teaching material of a particular course;

Competence to set goals for educational activities; Pindus Journal Of Culture, Literature, and Competence to understand the student, necessary for the implementation of an individual approach to education;

Competence on the subject (subject competence);

Competence to make decisions related to solving pedagogical problems;

Skills in developing activity and behavioral programs;

Competence in the organization of educational activities, which includes

The queue implies: organization of working conditions, first of all, information, competence corresponding to the set educational task;

Competence to achieve the student's understanding of the learning task and methods of its solution (methods of activity);

Competence to evaluate current and final performance.

CONCLUSION

In short, the organization of law classes requires pedagogical skills and competencies from the teacher. The use of new innovative pedagogical methods in the educational process also gives effective results.

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